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Chronospatial Frequency Of Fishing Gears Used Along The Ulhas River Estuary

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Abstract: Different kinds of fishing gears used along the Ulhas River estuary (URE) were studied for their make and methods of operation. Most of the gears were designed indigenously to suit the availability of the amenable fishery species. The overall chronospatial pattern of frequency of gears operation was obtained using PRIMER v6 software. The use of gears was most frequent and diverse towards the lower reaches of the estuary. Late post-monsoon season was the most affluent in gear frequency. The important fishing methods used along the URE was 'vana' (barrier net), 'busa' (surface gill-net), 'dol' (stationary bag net) and 'mali' (basin method for capturing mudskippers on mud-flats). The fishing was carried for subsistence or artisanal levels at major while commercial fishing was highly reduced in URE. The reduced mesh sizes of the ambient gears portray the size of the species sought which depicted the threatening status of overall condition of fisheries in URE and requires a special attention for its rejuvenation.

Keywords: Ulhas River estuary, fishing gears, subsistence, artisanal, fisheries, stationary bag nets, barrier nets, hand nets, traps, designs, fishery status, chronospatial, gear frequency, zonal, seasonal

Introduction:

The marine and inward water resources support the lively hood of the coastal people. Apart from the various resources the fisheries play important role in the economy of the coastal human habitations along the wetlands like creeks and estuaries. The estuarine part of Ulhas River commences from S-E near Dombivli region up streams; meanders for about 40 km before it joins the Arabian Sea towards N-W at Vasai (Bassein) creek and is situated between the latitude $18^{\circ} 45' 1019^{\circ} 19'$, N and longitude $73^{\circ} 21' 072^{\circ} 45'$, E on the world map and located near Thane City, Maharashtra State, India.

Ulhas River estuary (URE) is the important wetland imparting the pivotal role in sustaining the local fishermen population from decades. Chunk of the fishermen population of Thane City along the URE is dependent on the fisheries. As regards to this various types of traditional gears are used for capturing variety of important fin fisheries and shell fisheries along the URE since decades and yet have not been recorded earlier. In recent years due to the elevated incidences of various anthropogenic deteriorative activities the fisheries from URE have declined to the alarming level. Mangroves annihilation, domestic and increment in industrial waste water, reclamation activities, solid waste dumping are of common site along

Fig. 1: Map of Ulhas River estuary indicating the three zones from Dombivli to Ghodbunder Road. Zone-I extended from Dombivli to Kasheli Bridge; Zone-II from Kasheli bridge to Gaimukh and Zone-III from Gaimukh to Mira-Bhayandar. Zone-I was highly influenced by human habitations and agriculture, zone-II was impacted mostly due to industrial effluents and agriculture while zone-III being very wide and close to ocean was efficiently flushed with tidal currents and except the human habitation, at Mira-Bhayandar and some salt pans in the vicinity, it was not subjected to significant stresses.

the ambient water body. Therefore, most of the fishermen have abandoned the fisheries and have switched on to the alternative sources of income. The fishermen who have continued fishing are presently striving hard to procure catch at economic level but in vain. Accordingly the native fishing gears have been modified by the fishermen community to match the temperament of the available fisheries species in the ambient water bodies. The design of the gears of URE deviated greatly from those used along other regions of the India (Naik and Neelakantan, 1968; Kurian and Sebastian, 1976; Chakravartty and Sharma (2013); Islam *et al.*, 2013; Chourey *et al.*, 2014; Pijush, 2014).

Methodology:

The entire stretch of URE was divided for three zones as UZ-I, UZ-II and UZ-III as shown in the map (Fig.1). The zonal use of gears of along the estuary were observed, their operational methods and fishery species caught through them were recorded, on sites. The details of the materials used in making and design of gears were studied on sites or at the fishermen localities. The study was carried for two years from July 2004 to June 2006. Each year was divided into four seasons viz. MON (monsoon from July to September), EPM (early post-monsoon from October to December), LPM (late post-monsoon from January to March) and PRM (pre-monsoon from April to June) in present study (Fig.1).

Results and Discussion:

There were total 19 types of gears; hand gleaning and other methods in use for fishing purpose along entire stretch of URE. They are classified as stationary bag nets, barrier nets, gill nets, hand operated nets and basin method for capturing mudskippers. Three types each of stationary bag nets and barrier nets; two types of gill nets; various other methods; their local names, the material used for their construction and their operation was recorded (Table 1 and Fig. 2). All the nets were constructed using single sheet bend except gill net. Hand gleaning and 'malli' was practiced during low tide only.

Table 1 The classification of the gears on the basis of their designs used along the URE

Sr. No.	General Category of the Gear	Local Name of the Gear	Material used for construction
1	Stationary bag net	Dol, Patal and Bokshi	Synthetic, coir and/or cotton
2	Gill net	Busa, Pera	Synthetic
3	Barrier net	Vana, Pocha and Bund-net	Synthetic
3	Hand net	Bari, Paag, Zolva, Aasoo, Zile, Korbara, Pagoli (Fug), Gamcha and Gal	Synthetic, jute, coir and/or cotton
4	Hand gleaning	Used for capturing bivalves, mudskippers and crabs. Night-hand gleaning is associated with a light source to attract fish.	-----
5	'Malli' method (mudskipper trap)	Basin method of mudskippers trapping	Earthen pot or utensil and colorful cloth flags

It is well known from the past study that the lunar periodicity impact greatly on fishing (Desai, 1974; Ortega-Garcia, *et al.*, 2008; Limbini and Khan, 2012; Sajeevan and Sanadi, 2014; Das *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, present scenario of gear operations was based on lunar periodicity along the URE. Fishermen avoid fishing from 4th to 5th day of full moon and new moon days which they traditionally call as 'bhang' as catch is insignificant during these days. Some may go for fishing from 5th day ('Panchami') onwards till 10th day ('Dashami'). Fishermen call the period up to 'Dashami' as 'Udhan'. From 11th to 15th day is considered to be best for fishing since most fishery species appear only in this period in estuaries and creeks.

1. 'Dol' and 'Patal' (major stationary bag nets):

Dol and Patal are conical stationary bag nets, anteriorly opening with wide mouth and posteriorly by narrow cod end, measuring about 30 m in length, 30 m in width and 5 m in height. Both are made from synthetic secondary twines. Entire Dol net is mostly constructed through hand braiding with the mesh size decrement antero-posteriorly (maximum 120 mm to minimum 10 mm). Cod end has a finest mesh size (10 mm). Usually net is made of five circular parts antero-posteriorly as 'Mhor'; 'Chirata'; 'Katra'; 'Majola' and 'Khola' each being broader anteriorly

and narrower posteriorly to make a conical shape of the net. Whereas, Patal is made from machine made panels available in the local markets with a little variations in the mesh size (50 mm to 10 mm) from mouth towards cod end.

Operation: Dol and Patal nets are set in deep water to about 20 m in depth of the URE towards UZ-II and UZ-III against tidal current of flood tide and ebb tide. Two big heaps of stones each tied together in a net panel are used as master sinkers and attached to the lower corners of net with warps. Remaining two corners of the net are tied to the master floats (a cluster of big pieces polystyrene tied together in a small panel of fishing net) which support the upper part of mouth of the net. The master floats also help to mark the net's location. Third master float is tied to the middle part which helps in keeping net horizontal whereas fourth float is tied to the cod end. The tidal current brings fish which get filtered in the net. Fishes are hauled when tide turns. Small dug-out canoe, 'hodi' is used to operate the net and hauling the fish. Nets are used to capture number of marine and estuarine species viz. catfishes, sciaenids, clupeids, ribbon fish, target fishes, *Oreochromis mossambicus*, mullets, prawns, perches, ponyfishes, trevallies, snappers etc.

2. 'Bokshi' (minor stationary bag net):

Bokshi is a small net measuring 10 m in length and 1.5 m in height and width. The mesh size ranges from 20 mm to 5 mm antero-posteriorly in hand made version which is of rare site present days. The net is made from readymade netting panels available in the market with the uniform mesh size of 5 mm. mouth opens to about 1.5m wide and is guarded by two lateral wings flanking on either side. The wings are used to block the passage of fish from the sides when low tide commences.

Operation: The net is set in shallow inundated inward areas of narrow channels. The water is allowed to inundate during flood tide and net is set during ebb tide with the help of stakes on the bottom. The mouth and wings are

supported by number of stakes dependent on the width of the channel. The water is filtered while receding and the fishes are collected in the net and they are hauled from cod-end opening. Wide wings secure the escape of the fishes from the net. Various fishery species such as gobioids, prawns, mullets, catfishes, *Scatophagus argus*, *Terapon* spp. are caught in "bokshi" net. 'Bokshi' nets were frequently used in UZ-II during MON season for prawn fishing. Batteries of 'Bokshi' nets were arranged with the help of stakes inside the channel of URE at UZ-II during monsoon.

Fig. 2: The Types of Fishing Gears Used Along Ulhas River Estuary

1. Gamcha: Hand operated for capturing mysids

3. Bokshi net: Inward water net

5. Dol/ Patal net: Stationary bag nets

7. Mudskipper fishing by 'malli' method on the URE mudflats

2. Busa: Surface gill net

4. Pagoli or Fug net: Hoop-net

6. Korbara: Catch collection net

8. Hand gleaning for Mudskippers

9. Paag: Cast net operated in inundated waters

11. Vana: Barrier net set along the bank

13. Pocha: Inward water barrier net and 'jali' held by the fisherman

10. Zolva: The cradle net

12. Hand gleaning for bivalves

14. Aasoo: Shovel net

3. Gill nets:

Two types of gill nets were used viz. 'Busa' or 'Disco jali' for surface fishing and 'Pera' for bottom fishing. While 'Pera' being rarely used the 'Busa' was very common for its handy operation. The dimension was 30 to 50 m in length and 2 m in height with mesh sizes ranging from 100 mm to 20 mm. The nets made of light green colored mono-filament of synthetic material were constructed using double sheet bends. 'Busa' was common along the entire stretch of the URE.

Operation: 'Pera' were operated along the banks. The head rope was attached with weaker floats and the foot rope with stronger sinkers enabling the net to stand upright on the bottom. Whilst 'Busa' was attached with stronger floats and weaker sinkers on head rope and foot rope respectively to enable net to remain near the surface. 'Busa' were tied to the stern-spar of small boats like hodi or dug-out canoes and allowed to drift along the tidal currents. The 'Pera' were used to capture the bottom dwellers like catfishes and gobioids whereas 'Busa' were used for capturing *Oreochromis mossambicus*, mullets, sciaenids, clupeids and prawns.

4. Barrier nets:

Three types of barrier nets were commonly used along URE called as 'Vana', 'Pocha' and 'Bund' nets. 'Vana' was very common and was biggest gear in use along URE. It measured to about 500 m in length and 3 m in height. The mesh size ranged from minimum of 30 to maximum 100 mm. entire net was made from synthetic twine of second stage.

'Vana' measured nearly 200 to 500 m long and 2 m. in height with mesh size of 20 mm. The height of net may

vary dependent upon the depth of water, during high tide, at the location of its operation. 'Vana' was very frequently used along URE it was used seldom. It was designed for capturing *M. gulio* a target fish species as they habitually move at the bays in schools for feeding purpose. But during present study other species were also caught in 'Vana'.

Operation of 'vana': The net is kept pleated on one of the bank of the estuary during low tide which later at the full high tide level is tied on the bamboo stakes to keep it upright. As the water recedes during the low tide the fishes get filtered and retained by the net, which are then collected manually. 'Vana' was used to capture mullets in URE but variety of fishery species are captured with the help of this net.

'Pocha' was used in narrow inward channels for capturing giant fresh water prawns locally known as pocha. 'Pocha' wall net set in the narrow channels with the help of two lateral poles. The length of the net depends up on the width of the channel and height measures to about 2 m. the mesh size is 20 to 50 mm. net is either braided or machine made synthetic nettings are used to construct the 'Pocha'.

Operation of 'pocha': It is operated from small canoe made of fibre-plastic called hodi. The net is placed during ebb tide when water starts receding from the upstreams channels of the URE. Along with the giant fresh water prawns various species are caught in the 'pocha' viz. mullets, *Terapon* spp. *Scatophagus argus*, gobioids, *Sillago* spp. *Oreochromis mossambicus*, *Lates calcarifer*, *Mystus gulio* etc.

Sometimes small piece of rectangular panels of the net is used as a barrier for the fishes entered in the artificial

impoundments called as 'bund' net. Its size is defined by the opening of the impoundment and the mesh size ranges from 10 to 30 mm., it is made from the readymade nettings made of synthetic fibres. **Bund-net** is used at impoundments where fish coming along tidal waters are trapped and are raised for improving their size and taste. These nets avoid fish escape from ponds where they are reared. Bund-nets allow tidal water, so that it brings food and oxygenated water while inundating from URE and carry away the waste and depleted water back with receding current. Species like *Mystus gulio*, *Mugil spp.*, *L. calcarifer* and tiger prawns are trapped which are sought for rearing in such impoundments. Most of the catches are consumed by pond owner, Such fishery is called as of 'subsistence' type.

5. Hand nets:

There were numerous hand operated nets or traps used along the URE e.g. drag net, 'Yeri' (khecha); cast net, 'paag'; water wading traps, cradle net, 'zolva'; shovel net, 'Aasoo'; mysids net, 'Zile', hoop net, 'Pagoli' or fug net; a simple hand line, 'Gal'; a cloth net, 'Gamcha'; scoop net, 'Jali' and fish collection net, 'Korbara'. All are operated in shallow inundated waters. Yeri and Paag nets are made from cotton twine or synthetic fibres.

Yeri is a small rectangular net panel measuring 5 to 7 m in length and 1.5 m in height and has mesh size of 10 mm. A 2 m long bamboo pole is tied at each flank of the net by hitching method. The flank-bamboos are held by two fishermen (one on each side) to dragged the net in chest deep water during high tide. Mostly mullets and seldom *Megalops cyprinoides*, *Oreochromis mossambicus*, *Lates calcarifer* and *Terapon spp.* are captured.

Paag is a handmade circular cast net made from cotton twines or synthetic fibres with mesh size of 10 mm. Similar net was reported by various experts from all over the India (Kumar and Kumar, 2013; Chourey *et al.*, 2014; Laxmappa and Bakshi, 2014). This is a circular net tide with a hand line (casting cord) in the center. The peripheral margin is attached with a series of lead sinkers to enhance the sinking speed and ultimately closing of net due to inertia. Being small in diameter the net lacks with brace lines and hence no peripheral pockets are formed unlike those were found along Kulsi River Assam (Islam, *et al.*, 2013). The cast net without pockets was also reported by Naik and Neelakantan (1988). It is operated in shallow water from hodi (canoe) or from the banks. This net is thrown with a skill full yank so as to spread it before it falls on the water surface. Then it is allowed to sink to certain level and is closed with a small tug before it reaches the bottom. The net is then hauled slowly and fishes are secured.

Zolva is a rectangular piece of netting made from synthetic twine of 10 to 20 mm mesh size (mostly hand braided) and supported by two lateral slender bamboo poles which are tied to the net by hitching. It is operated in knee high water to capture octopus, crabs, cuttlefish, catfish, *Oreochromis mossambicus* etc. mostly during MON.

Aasoo is a pear shaped shovel net made of 15 to 20 mm mesh size netting constructed from synthetic fibres and is supported laterally by two slender bamboo poles and anteriorly by an steel bar which is bent in a 'C' shaped form. Bamboo poles are crossed at posterior end at an angle of about 50 to 60 degrees and tied together with the synthetic rope. A conical net panel is reeved by a thick synthetic rope at the edges before it is hitched at regular interval on the triangular frame to make a pear-shaped concave form. The tapering end of the netting remains hanging towards the posterior where it is hinged to the crossing of the poles with a synthetic rope. One of the lateral bamboos is kept longer to be used as a handle while operation. The horizontal steel bar enables the fishermen to thrust the net into mud to capture bottom fishes like mullets, gobioids and crabs. The depth of the net ensures the fish after being scooped out from the mud also the mud is washed off by swinging the net in water before the fish is hauled in a tiny split bamboo basket.

Pagoli is a hoop net used to capture crabs in shallow water. It is operated from the temporary personal buoy made of vehicular rubber tube. The air filled tube is weaved with nylon rope to construct the seat in the centre for a fisherman who sits on it keeping legs hanging in the water while fishing. The trap has synthetic netting of mesh size 70 mm, supported by iron ring of 30 to 40 cm diameter. There is a horizontal rope tied on ring along diameter where bait is attached. Polychaete worms, trash fish or dough are used as bait. The trap is lowered in water from banks or from rubber tube buoy and lifted, suddenly, after a considerable time, to haul the crabs (*Neptunus spp.*).

Zile is fine meshed (10-50 mm) circular hand net used to capture mud-crabs during winter season. It is supported by a circular frame made of plastic pipe of a diameter of about 65 to 75 cm holding a conical net of 100 cm depth. The net is operated just like 'Pagoli' or 'Fug' scoop nets for capturing mud crabs (*Scylla serrata*). Similar gear was reported by Nirmale *et al.* (2012) along the Ratnagiri Coast.

Gal a simple hand lines is used for capturing catfishes during MON. It is very crude type of gear, in which the line (synthetic monofilament twine) may or may not be tied with a bamboo pole. A hook is tied at the terminal end of about 5 m long twine which is supported by a small

horizontal stick at a distance of 50 to 100 cm. This stick works as a float and as indicator when fish gets hooked. The assembly is locally known as 'Gal'. Polychaete worms and trash fishes are used as bait. The line is lifted with a jerk when the float stick starts bumping on water surface and fish is removed from the hook.

Gamcha is small piece of cloth with fine knit cotton fibres measuring about 2 m. in length and 1 m. in breadth. Traditionally 'Gamcha' is commonly found with men and used variously at personal level like a hand-napkin for cleaning; wiping etc. it is also used to trap very tiny organisms like *Acetes indicus* (mysids) or *Indomysis annandalei* which are highly relished by local fishermen community locally known as 'Jawala and 'Refa'/'Kolin' respectively. It is operated in the inundated shallow waters downstream of URE during MON, EPM and LPM seasons. 'Gamcha' is held under water surface by two or more persons and water is allowed to flow above it. After finding ample swarm of tiny organisms above 'gamcha' it is slowly lifted and allowed to filter water through the mesh. The catch is scooped with hand conveniently and collected in the container.

Jali and **Korbara** are fish collecting hand-nets. Jali is supported by triangular frame made of two cross sticks. One of the stick is longer to function as handle. The net is supported at anterior end with a rope reeving through the net edge anteriorly. The net is commonly used in giant fresh water prawn fishing with the help of pocha. Also is used to scoop the fish out from bigger nets. The fishes are hauled in conical net called Korbara which is used for cleaning, sorting and carrying the fish to the landing spot.

6. Hand Gleaning:

There were frequent instances of hand picking method used to catch fishes or shellfish. Mudskippers, bivalves (clams, cockles, mussels & edible oysters) or crabs (*Scylla serrata*) are captured with bare hand in shallow (knee high) water or on the exposed mudflats during low tides. *Scylla serrata* are captured during night using lamp or torch. Crabs get attracted towards light and fall easy catch. This phenomenon may be referred as 'light fishing'. For capturing mudskipper, fishermen walk on mudflats where the fresh burrows are seen. Hands are then forced into mud around the burrow in a 'polar-bear' style to about two feet deep. A lump of mud is separated from the rest with a jerk along with fish, perhaps entangled, which is then slowly isolated using fingers and dropped in the split-bamboo basket. In bivalves gleaning a wooden plank curved from bottom is used for sliding on sinking mudflats. Fisherman kneels on the plank with one leg and another leg is used to push the plank ahead by thrusting.

The fresh burrows of clams and cockles are observed to capture bivalves like *Meretrix* spp., *Catylasia* spp., *Anadara granosa*, *Cardium asiaticum*, *Paphia malabarica*, *Crassostrea* spp. captured from exposed bottoms of ambient waters.

7. 'Malli' –the mudskipper trapping method:

Malli—Mudskipper trap Fug-crab trap were overwhelming in URE. The mudskipper fishing is carried out mostly setting a trap on the mudflats involved 'basin-method', locally known as 'Malli' (Rathod, 2005). The mudskipper fishing occurred only on northern bank of URE since there was considerable deterioration occurred due to the human intrusion on the southern bank. 'Malli', the technique, is based on suffocation of the fish by plastering mud on the burrow's openings. A rectangular or triangular embankment is constructed out of mixture of mud and piles of rice straws on the mudflat during low tide. A slope is maintained towards one of the corners, where an earthen or metal container is buried in the soil, keeping its mouth (brim) open at ground level called as 'Hundi'. Due to suffocation the mudskippers emerge on the surface are scared with colourful cloths to drive them in the 'hundi'. Fish is hauled after a considerable number of individuals are trapped in 'hundi'.

Fig. 3: Chronospatial Fishing Gears Frequency Along URE

PCO was run after obtaining resemblance of samples in Euclidean distance matrix to depict the spatio-temporal relationship of the frequency of fishing gears used along the URE. Data represented 87.2% of variations in gear frequency. Abbreviations: Van = vana; Dol = 'dol' or 'patal' net; Bo = bokshi; Bar = 'bari' net; GN = Gill nets 'busa' or 'pera'; MT = mudskippers trapping; HOG = hand operated gears; Po = 'pocha'; HP = hand picking and HL = hand line.

8. Chronospatial frequency of gears use along URE:

Frequency of operation of various gears was prevalent towards the mouth of the URE. Most frequent gears used were vana (Van), dol & patal (Dol), bokshi (Bo), gill nets (GN), mudskipper trapping (MT) and hand operated gears (HOG). However, pochha (Po), bari (Bar), hand picking (HP) and hand line (HL) operations were insignificant amongst the others. Dol (Dol), bokshi (Bo), gill nets (GN) and mudskipper fishing (MT) were very frequent in URE. UZ-III was richest while UZ-I was poorest in gears frequency of operation. According to earlier study it was observed that gears frequency increases with the available fisheries (Islam *et al.*, 2013). Dol operation was most frequent in UZ-III. Although MON season had lucrative catches the heavy raining and flooding obliterated the frequency of gear operations except in UZ-II where the prawn fishing was overwhelming with help of 'Bokshi' net. Fishing activity was prominent in UZ-I, UZ-II during both MON and LPM indicating these as major fishing seasons whereas in UZ-III, LPM being very frequent followed by PRM and EPM (Fig. 3). Overall frequency of gears operation was lowest in MON (except bokshi) and highest in LPM in ambient waterbody.

Conclusion:

Total 19 kinds of fish procuring methods were used along URE mostly of non-selective type and were implied for subsistence or artisanal fisheries particularly in upper zones of the estuary. Most prosperous zone and seasons were UZ-III and LPM respectively. Most important gears in URE were dol, gill net, vana, mudskipper trapping, bokshi and hand operated gears. Dol and Patal were not used in UZ-I. Gill nets, 'bari' and hand operated gears were randomly used along entire stretch of the URE. 'Bokshi' was common in MON season for prawn fishing. In UZ-III limited commercial fishing occurred with the help of dol, vana and gill nets. The gears were indigenously designed and were having finer mesh size to suit the sizes of the amenable species. It has been also found that these gears are still in use along the URE. The reduced mesh sizes of the gears to ensure better catch have consequently enhanced the overfishing in URE. This indicated that fisheries of URE have declined to non-commercial level.

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